

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

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Project title: Improving variant effect predictions of regulatory sequences in human disease using Machine Learning and High-throughput Assays

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2 Summary

2.1 In English

The project aimed to advance the prediction of regulatory variant effects in human disease by integrating high-throughput Massively Parallel Reporter Assays (MPRAs) with modern machine learning (ML) approaches. Recognizing that an unknown proportion of disease-associated genetic variants reside in non-coding regions, this work sought to overcome the limitations of both incomplete functional annotation and insufficient training data for ML-based variant effect prediction.

Using the lentiMPRA system, we tested over 170,000 variants across more than 64,000 candidate cis-regulatory elements in multiple cell types, selected via a deep neural network trained on open chromatin data from diverse cell lines. Additional large-scale lentiMPRA experiments enabled the functional characterization of transcriptional regulatory elements; for example, promoters exhibited orientation bias and broad activity, while enhancers displayed increased tissue specificity.

Trained convolutional neural network models demonstrated high accuracy in predicting regulatory activity and sequence function, as well as improved identification of cell-type-specific regulatory grammar. These models outperformed existing methods such as Sei and Enformer in variant effect prediction, and we validated their biological relevance by identifying key transcription factor motifs learned by the models. The resulting MPRA datasets, software tools, and standards for data processing and quality control have been broadly adopted in the community and by the IGVF consortium.

The integration of regulatory variant effect predictions into the CADD framework further enhanced genome-wide variant prioritization, as demonstrated across multiple benchmarking datasets and clinical applications. All raw and processed data, computational models, and software are openly available, ensuring reusability and transparency. Overall, the project established new gold-standard resources and methods for regulatory variant interpretation, directly supporting research and clinical applications.

2.2 In German

Das Projekt zielte darauf ab, die Vorhersage regulatorischer Varianteneffekte bei menschlichen Erkrankungen durch die Integration von Massively Parallel Reporter Assays (MPRAs) mit modernen Methoden des maschinellen Lernens (ML) voranzubringen. Unter der Erkenntnis, dass ein unbekannter Anteil krankheitsassoziierter genetischer Varianten in nicht-kodierenden Regionen liegt, wurde versucht, die Einschränkungen sowohl unvollständiger funktioneller Annotation als auch unzureichender Trainingsdaten für ML-basierte Varianteneffektvorhersagen zu überwinden.

Mit dem lentiMPRA-System testeten wir über 170.000 Varianten in mehr als 64.000 potenziellen cis-regulatorischen Elementen in verschiedenen Zelltypen, ausgewählt durch ein tiefes neuronales Netz das auf offenem Chromatin in verschiedener Zelllinien trainierten. Weitere lentiMPRA-Experimente ermöglichten die funktionelle Charakterisierung transkriptioneller regulatorischer Elemente; beispielsweise zeigten Promotoren eine Orientierungsabhängigkeit und breite Aktivität, während Enhancer eine erhöhte Gewebespezifität aufwiesen.

Trainierte Convolutional Neural Network-Modelle zeigten eine hohe Genauigkeit bei der Vorhersage regulatorischer Aktivität und Sequenzfunktion sowie eine verbesserte Identifikation zelltypspezifischer

regulatorischer Grammatik. Diese Modelle übertrafen bestehende Methoden wie Sei und Enformer bei der Varianteneffektvorhersage, und wir validierten ihre biologische Relevanz durch die Identifizierung wichtiger, von den Modellen gelernter Transkriptionsfaktor-Motive. Die resultierenden MPRA-Datensätze, Softwaretools und Standards für Datenverarbeitung und Qualitätskontrolle wurden in der Community und vom IGVF-Konsortium übernommen.

Die Integration der Vorhersagen regulatorischer Varianteneffekte in das CADD-Framework verbesserte zudem die genomweite Priorisierung von Varianten, wie anhand mehrerer Benchmarking-Datensätze und klinischer Anwendungen gezeigt werden konnte. Sämtliche Roh- und verarbeiteten Daten, Rechenmodelle und Software stehen offen zur Verfügung, was Wiederverwendbarkeit und Transparenz gewährleistet. Insgesamt wurden im Projekt neue Goldstandard-Ressourcen und -Methoden für die Interpretation regulatorischer Varianten geschaffen, die Forschung und klinische Anwendungen direkt unterstützen.

3 Progress Report

3.1 Background

Studies have shown that most genetic variants associated with common diseases, as well as an unknown proportion of causal variants for rare diseases, fall into non-coding regions of the human genome. While research has traditionally focused on the about 2% of the genome that codes for proteins, regulatory changes in non-coding regions—such as promoters and distal regulatory elements—play a crucial role in human phenotypic variation and disease. Despite advances in cataloging regulatory elements along the human genome, the functional impact of most non-coding variants remains unknown. High-throughput experimental methods like Massively Parallel Reporter Assays (MPRAs) have emerged as powerful tools for measuring the regulatory activity of thousands of variants in parallel. However, existing MPRA datasets are limited in scope, often focusing on specific loci, single cell types, or studying frequent population variants. Furthermore, the subtle and context-dependent effects of regulatory variants make their interpretation challenging.

In parallel, machine learning (ML) approaches, especially deep learning methods, have shown promise for predicting the effects of genetic variants. Yet, the lack of comprehensive, high-quality training data of regulatory variants, and the cell-type specificity of regulatory effects, have limited the effectiveness and generalizability of these models. The integration of ML with high-throughput functional assays presents a unique opportunity to close this gap, providing both the data and analytical frameworks needed to advance variant effect prediction.

3.2 Objectives

The overall aim of this project is to develop improved, genome-wide predictors of regulatory variant effects using a combination of advanced machine learning algorithms and high-throughput functional assays. The specific objectives are:

1. *Develop a novel variant selection strategy for MPRA testing:* Use deep neural networks (DNNs) trained on sequence data from open chromatin regions across multiple cell types to prioritize and

select variants for functional testing. This approach will enable the creation of a comprehensive and unbiased variant set for MPRA experiments, capturing activating, repressing, neutral, and tissue-specific effects on a genome-wide scale.

2. *Gain insights into regulatory mechanisms through DNN model interpretation and high-complexity MPRA experiments across cell-types:* Perform MPRA experiments on more than 120,000 variants distributed across over 60,000 genomic regions in multiple cell lines. Analyze the resulting data to obtain quantitative measurements of regulatory variant effects and study them in relation to epigenomic features annotated for the corresponding genomic location. Build sequence-based models from the data and interpret them to dissect the regulatory grammar of the genome.
3. *Build and validate improved predictive models of regulatory variant effects and integrate them into a framework for genome-wide variant effect prediction (CADD):* Use results from the MPRA experiments and DNN interpretation to inform a new generation of computational models for regulatory variant effect prediction. Incorporate these models into the widely used Combined Annotation Dependent Depletion (CADD) framework for genome-wide variant effect prediction.

3.3 Results and findings

Massively parallel characterization of transcriptional regulatory elements

Before starting to understand variant effects, a systematic study of regulatory element activity can provide important insights into cell-type specific regulators. With our collaborators, we used MPRA to test the regulatory activity of more than 680,000 sequences, a comprehensive set of annotated candidate cis-regulatory elements (cCREs) among three cell types (HepG2, K562 and WTC11) and found that 41.7% of these sequences were active. By testing sequences in both orientations, we find promoters to have strand-orientation biases and their 200-nucleotide cores to function as non-cell-type-specific 'on switches' with activities highly correlated to the expression levels of their associated genes. By contrast, enhancers have weaker orientation biases, but increased tissue-specific characteristics. Utilizing the lentivirus-based MPRA (lentiMPRA) data, we develop sequence-based models to predict cCRE function and variant effects with high accuracy, delineate regulatory motifs and model their combinatorial effects. We show that convolutional neural networks (CNNs) with limited parameter complexity, capture cell-type specific activity while providing computational scale and interpretability. Testing a lentiMPRA library encompassing 60,000 cCREs in all three cell types further identified factors that determine cell-type specificity. Collectively, our work provides an extensive catalogue of functional CREs in three widely used cell lines and showcases how large-scale functional measurements can be used to dissect regulatory grammar. For more details, refer to our publication Agarwal *et al.* 2025¹ in the journal Nature.

Massively parallel characterization of variants within regulatory elements

Slightly exceeding scale of the proposed MPRA design, 170,000 variants from 64,000 cCREs were selected using sequenced-based CNNs trained on DNase-seq data of seven well studied ENCODE cell lines (see Schubach *et al.* 2024² for the publication of regulatory sequence model). LentiMPRA was conducted in HepG2 and HEK293T cell lines and experiments showed high correlation across

replicates (n=3) for both cell lines (see Figure 1A). We re-trained our CNN model, MPRAnn¹, on both experiments, resulting in similar activity prediction nearly matching the replicate correlation (see Figure 1B). By performing in-silico mutagenesis and extracting attention scores, we demonstrated that the model learned the key transcription factors involved, as shown in Figure 1C.

Variant effect prediction showed lower correlation but outperformed state-of-the-art models such as Sei³ and Enformer⁴ (Figure 2A). Using BCalm⁵, we tested for significant variants and retained about 22% of active variants in HepG2 and 12 % in HEK293T (see Figure 2B). This proportion is higher than expected, in line with our initial variant selection strategy using a regulatory model trained on seven cell lines. Figure 2C shows examples where significant variants either disrupt or create new motifs, thereby altering the regulatory transcription of the element. With these results, we are confident that our data provides an ideal benchmark for regulatory variant effects, not limited to specific loci or standing variation, and available across multiple cell types. We expect regulatory variant prediction of future tools to be benchmarked with it. Raw and processed data are accessible via the IGVF portal IDs: IGVFDS1589ODOW (library and assignment), IGVFSM9009DVDG (HepG2), and IGVFSM8026MGEJ (HEK293T).

Figure 1: **A** Heatmap depicting Pearson correlation of $\log_2(\text{RNA/DNA})$ among replicates (n=3) in HepG2 (left) and HEK293T (right) cell lines. The upper diagonal shows scatterplots of all sequences between each replicate. **B** Scatterplots of predicted (MPRAnn) versus observed MPRA activity in HepG2 (left), and HEK293T (right) in the test dataset. The r value is the Pearson correlation coefficient.

C Important enriched motifs in MPRAnn identified by TF-MoDISco-lite in HepG2 (left) and HEK293T (right).

Figure 2: **A** Scatterplot comparing predicted variant effects (X-axis) with MPRAnn-measured variant effects (Y-axis) in HepG2 (top) and HEK293T (bottom). Normalized model predictions are shown for Enformer ($ALT_{DNase} - REF_{DNase}$), MPRAnn ($ALT-REF$), and DeepSEA Sei ($ALT_{DNase} - REF_{DNase}$). **B** Volcano plot showing log₂ fold change (logFC) and -log₁₀ FDR-adjusted p-value for differentially expressed variants. Significant variants (FDR < 0.1) are color-coded: up-regulating (yellow), down-regulating (blue), and non-significant (grey). The dashed line indicates the 10% FDR threshold. **C** Examples of significant variants either creating (green) or disrupting (red) binding of GABPA, USF2, HNF1B, KLF16 in HepG2 cell-line.

*Tool and method development for MPRA*s

We developed several tools for the scientific community to analyze MPRA data. In Keukeleire *et al.* 2025⁵, we introduced BCalm, an MPRA analysis framework designed to address limitations of existing tools. BCalm models individual barcode counts rather than aggregating per sequence, increasing statistical power and robustness to outliers while remaining fast and precise. We demonstrate improved performance over existing methods on both simulated MPRA data and our MPRA library in HepG2 and HEK293T cells. We developed the fast and scalable pipeline MPRAsnakeflow to process sequencing

data from MPRA into count tables for candidate sequences tested in the experiment. MPRAsnakeflow is now the standard MPRA analysis pipeline for the IGVF consortium⁶. More tools are listed in Section 4.2.

Improvement of genome-wide variant predictions

With Combined Annotation Dependent Depletion (CADD) v1.7, a method for genome-wide prioritization of variants across different molecular functions, we integrated new annotation features, among them protein language model scores (Meta ESM-1v), regulatory variant effect predictions (from sequence-based CNNs trained on open chromatin data and architectures optimized by our MPRA work) and sequence conservation scores (Zoonomia). We could show that the inclusion of new features further improved the overall performance of CADD using a variety of different benchmarks. All results can be found in Schubach et al. 2024².

3.4 Deviations

LentiMPRA was performed in two instead of four cell-types proposed originally. The first experiment with four cell-types failed. Failed data will be part of a manuscript on “Best Practices for Massively Parallel Reporter Assays” that includes troubleshooting of MPRA experiments.

3.5 Research data handing and data infrastructures

Within this research project, all raw data has been published to open data repositories. Sequencing data from the MPRA experiments and processing pipeline results have been made openly available via the ENCODE portal (<https://www.encodeproject.org>) and the IGVF portal (<https://data.igvf.org>). Software, scripts, and sequence-based models are openly accessible on GitHub under an open-source license. Where applicable, software and workflow pipelines are version-controlled using semantic versioning, and specific versions are cited for processed data. Processed data is uploaded to the open science framework Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>).

For CADD, a website provides access to pre-computed, indexed genome-wide scores. Users can also access CADD via an API or through a user interface to upload variants for scoring. To minimize the risk of downtime, we operate redundant instances: a German-based server (<https://cadd.kircherlab.bi-health.org>) and a US-based server (<https://cadd.gs.washington.edu>). All computations were performed on the HPC for Research cluster at the Berlin Institute of Health at Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin.

3.6 Developed re-usable and accessible data, methods, standards, software or infrastructures

3.6.1 MPRA experiments

Massively parallel characterization of transcriptional regulatory elements¹

- Raw sequencing data and processed files (ENCODE ID):
Pilot libraries (HepG2: [ENCSR463IRX](#); K562: [ENCSR460LZI](#)); Large-scale libraries (HepG2: [ENCSR022GQD](#); K562: [ENCSR382BVV](#); WTC11: [ENCSR244FWB](#)); Joint libraries (HepG2: [ENCSR405QCT](#); K562: [ENCSR203UFY](#); WTC11: [ENCSR336MKI](#))
- Pretrained models: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.03.05.531189>

Massively parallel characterization of variants within regulatory elements

- Raw sequencing and processed files:

Library: [IGVFDS1589ODOW](#); HEK293T: [IGVFMS8026MGEJ](#); HepG2: [IGVFMS9009DVDG](#)

3.6.2 Software and methods

We have developed a comprehensive suite of software libraries, as well as processing and analysis pipelines for MPRA. All tools are open-source and extensively documented, including detailed tutorials. To ensure easy distribution and reproducibility, we use containerization technologies (Docker, Apptainer) and the cross-platform, language-agnostic package and environment management system conda. CADD scores are widely used within the genomics community, in routine genetic diagnostics applications, fine-mapping of GWAS data, building meta-classifiers, and annotating datasets. CADD is freely available for non-commercial applications and can be licensed by the University of Washington for commercial projects. We provide a workflow for offline installation (CADD-scripts), as well as a website with both an API and a user interface for score computation. All software and methods developed within this research project are listed in Section 4.2 – Category B.

3.6.3 Standards

Together with the IGVF consortium, we have defined metadata, design, file format and quality control standards for MPRA experiments. We developed a pipeline (MPRAsnakeflow) that is being used across labs and experimental designs to ease accessibility to MPRA.

3.7 Bibliography

1. Agarwal, V. *et al.* Massively parallel characterization of transcriptional regulatory elements. *Nature* 1–10 (2025) doi:10.1038/s41586-024-08430-9.
2. Schubach, M., Maass, T., Nazaretyan, L., Röner, S. & Kircher, M. CADD v1.7: using protein language models, regulatory CNNs and other nucleotide-level scores to improve genome-wide variant predictions. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **52**, D1143–D1154 (2024).
3. Chen, K. M., Wong, A. K., Troyanskaya, O. G. & Zhou, J. A sequence-based global map of regulatory activity for deciphering human genetics. *Nat. Genet.* **54**, 940–949 (2022).
4. Avsec, Ž. *et al.* Effective gene expression prediction from sequence by integrating long-range interactions. *Nat. Methods* **18**, 1196–1203 (2021).
5. Keukeleire, P. *et al.* Using individual barcodes to increase quantification power of massively parallel reporter assays. *BMC Bioinformatics* **26**, 52 (2025).
6. Engreitz, J. M. *et al.* Deciphering the impact of genomic variation on function. *Nature* **633**, 47–57 (2024).
7. Gordon, M. G. *et al.* lentiMPRA and MPRAflow for high-throughput functional characterization of gene regulatory elements. *Nat. Protoc.* **15**, 2387–2412 (2020).
8. Rafi, A. M. *et al.* A community effort to optimize sequence-based deep learning models of gene regulation. *Nat. Biotechnol.* 1–11 (2024) doi:10.1038/s41587-024-02414-w.

4 Published Project Results

4.1 Category A – Articles in peer-reviewed journals, contributions to peer-reviewed conferences or to anthology volumes, and book publications

Articles in peer-reviewed journals (4):

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft

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Agarwal, V., Inoue, F., Schubach, M., *et al.* Massively Parallel Characterization of Transcriptional Regulatory Elements. *Nature* 1–10 (2025) doi: [10.1038/s41586-024-08430-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-08430-9).

Keukeleire, P., Rosen, J. D., Göbel-Knapp, A., Salomon, K., Schubach, M., Kircher, M. Using Individual Barcodes to Increase Quantification Power of Massively Parallel Reporter Assays. *BMC Bioinformatics*. **26**, 52 (2025) doi: [10.1186/s12859-025-06065-9](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-025-06065-9).

Rafi, A. M., *et al.* A Community Effort to Optimize Sequence-Based Deep Learning Models of Gene Regulation. *Nat, Biotechnol.* 1-11 (2024) doi: [10.1038/s41587-024-02414-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-024-02414-w).

Schubach, M., *et al.* CADD v1.7: Using Protein Language Models, Regulatory CNNs and Other Nucleotide-Level Scores to Improve Genome-Wide Variant Predictions. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **52**, D1143–D1154 (2024) doi: [10.1093/nar/gkad989](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad989).

Contributions to peer-reviewed conferences (5 talks, 3 posters):

Dash, P. M., Deng, C., Shendure, J., Ahituv, N., Kircher, M., Schubach, M. Integrating high-throughput assays and deep learning for characterization of human cis-regulatory elements *European Society of Human Genetics Meeting (ESHG)*. (2024) Berlin, Germany. Presentation type: poster

Schubach, M., Maass, T., Nazaretyan, L., Röner, S., Kircher, M. CADD v1.7: using protein language models, regulatory CNNs and other nucleotide-level scores to improve genome-wide variant predictions. *European Society of Human Genetics Meeting (ESHG)*. (2024) Berlin, Germany. Presentation type: talk

Dash, P. M., Schubach, M., Deng, C., Shendure, J., Ahituv, N., Kircher, M. Accelerating high-throughput characterization of regulatory variants with deep learning. *Regulatory & Systems Genomics with DREAM Challenges (RSGDREAM)*. (2024) Madison, Wisconsin, USA. Presentation type: talk

Dash, P. M., Schubach, M., Deng, C., Shendure, J., Ahituv, N., Kircher, M. Accelerating high-throughput characterization of regulatory variants with deep learning. *Kipoi Summit*. (2023) Zugspitze, Germany. Presentation type: talk

Agarwal, V., Inoue, F., Schubach, M., Martin, B. K., Dash, P. M., *et al.* Massively parallel characterization of transcriptional regulatory elements in three diverse human cell types. *Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology/European Conference on Computational Biology (ISMB/ECCB)*. (2023) Lyon, France. Presentation type: talk

Schubach, M., Dash, P. M., Deng, C., Shendure, J., Ahituv, N., Kircher, M. Deep learning-assisted selection of regulatory variants for high-throughput experimental testing. *Gesellschaft für Humangenetik (GfH)* (2023) Kassel, Germany. Presentation type: talk

Dash, P. M., Schubach, M., Kircher, M. A sustainable workflow for MPRA data analysis: MPRAsnakeflow. *European Conference on Computational Biology (ECCB)* (2022) Barcelona, Spain. Presentation type: poster

Dash, P. M., Schubach, M., Kircher, M. MPRAsnakeflow: A Snakemake based framework for MPRA data analysis. *Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology (ISMB)* (2022) Madison, Wisconsin, USA.
Presentation type: poster

4.2 Category B – Any other form of published results

MPRAsnakeflow: A computational pipeline designed to process sequencing data from MPRA to create count tables for candidate sequences tested in the experiment.

- Software repository: <https://github.com/kircherlab/MPRAsnakeflow>
- Documentation: <https://mprasnaflow.readthedocs.io>
- Tutorial with interactive notebook: https://github.com/kircherlab/MPRAsnakeflow_tutorial

MPRAOligoDesign: Workflow generating an MPRA oligo design from variants and regions.

- Software repository: <https://github.com/kircherlab/MPRAOligoDesign>
- Documentation: <https://mpraoligodesign.readthedocs.io>

MPRALib: Python library with a command-line interface for analyzing, modifying and plotting processed MPRA count data (e.g. generated with MPRAsnakeflow).

- Software repository: <https://github.com/kircherlab/MPRALib>
- Documentation: <https://mpralib.readthedocs.io>

IGVF MPRA quantification workflow: Compute robust quantifications using BCalm and generate genome browser tracks for variants or elements from MPRA counts.

- Software repository: https://github.com/kircherlab/IGVF_MPRA_quantification
- Documentation: https://github.com/kircherlab/IGVF_MPRA_quantification/blob/master/README.md

CADD²: Scoring deleteriousness of short sequence variants (SNVs, MNVs, indels) across the human genome, freely available for all non-commercial applications. We provide pre-computed CADD-based scores (C-scores) for all 9 billion possible SNVs, prescore population MNVs and indels from aggregation efforts, and enable scoring of additional variants on our website. In addition, we maintain a workflow, CADD-scripts, for offline scoring of variants.

- CADD website: <https://cadd.bihealth.org/>
- CADD-scripts: <https://github.com/kircherlab/CADD-scripts>

MPRAnn: A workflow to generate DNA sequence-based CNN models from genomic DNA sequences predicting MPRA activity for e.g., $\log(\text{RNA}/\text{DNA})$ values.

- Software repository: https://github.com/visze/sequence_cnn_models
- Documentation: https://github.com/visze/sequence_cnn_models/blob/master/README.md

BCalm⁵: R package that provides tools for differential analysis in MPRA studies. It allows users to use individual barcodes as model input.

- Software repository: <https://github.com/kircherlab/BCalm>
- Documentation: <https://github.com/kircherlab/BCalm/blob/master/README.md>